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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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INTERNATIONAL LAW AND DIPLOMACY: CHALLENGING THE “FIXITY” OF STATE SOVEREIGNTY

By

Nelson E. Chegwe*, Michael C. Ogwezzy**

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ABSTRACT

The notion of state sovereignty, which pertains to a state's exclusive authority and autonomy to govern itself without external intervention, is fundamental to international law. Over time, the idea of sovereignty has changed. A more nuanced meaning that acknowledges the interdependence and interconnection of nations in the modern world has replaced the conventional view of absolute sovereignty. The purpose of this research paper is to investigate the idea of state sovereignty in international law by following its historical evolution and looking at how it is now used in modern international relations. Using the doctrinal approach, the study assesses the tensions and conflicts that might occur between the concepts of state sovereignty and the necessity for international collaboration and governance in areas such as human rights, commerce, and environmental protection. Additionally, the paper examines the ways in which state sovereignty is limited, such as the recognition of specific rights and obligations of states under international law, the function of international organizations, and the principle of responsibility to protect when there are flagrant violations of human rights. In summary, this essay contends that although state sovereignty is still a cornerstone of international law, its application and understanding must be considered in light of the intricately linked global system in which states function.

Key Word: *International Law, Fixity, Sovereignty, Diplomacy, State.*

1. INTRODUCTION.

Sovereignty is the central organizing principle of the system of states. However, it is also one of the most controversial concepts in international relations. Essentially, sovereignty means possession of absolute authority within a bounded territorial space¹. There is internal and external sovereignty. Internally, a sovereign government is a fixed authority with a settled population that possesses a monopoly on the use of force. It is the supreme authority within that territory. Externally, sovereignty is the entry visa into the committee of states recognized by other states as possessing territorial integrity and right of participation in diplomacy and international organization on equal footing with other states.

Sovereignty has been a source of stability for more than two hundred years². It has fostered world order by establishing legal protection against external intervention and by offering a diplomatic foundation for the negotiation of treaties, the formation of international organizations and the development of international law. Sovereignty has been a source of stability for more than two hundred years. It has fostered world order by establishing legal protection against external intervention and by offering a diplomatic foundation for the negotiation of treaties, the formation of international organizations and the development of international law.

Underscoring the importance of state sovereignty is an explicit prohibition on the United Nations Organizations from interfering in the domestic affairs of member states. Accordingly, Article 2(7) provides that “nothing contained in the present charter shall authorize the United Nations to intervene in matters that are essentially within the domestic jurisdiction of any state or shall require the member to submit such matters to settlement under the present Charter”. Thus, sovereignty is a key constitutional safeguard of international order and the central organizing principle of

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¹ Nico Shrijver, “The Changing Nature of State Sovereignty” *The British Year Book of International Law* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2000), PP. 69 – 70

² Mohammed Ayob, “The New Old Disorder in the Third World” (*Global Governance* 1, 1995), PP 59 – 70.

the system of states that provides the foundation for the conventional separation of modern politics into domestic and international spheres³.

In recent times however, international relation theorists have devoted sufficient attention to the processes through which state sovereignty is being transformed in the modern world. The human right issue for example, offers a case study of a gradual and significant re-conceptualization of state sovereignty while the emergence of a whole range of trans-border issues such as economic globalization, environmental concern and terrorism have led many observers to question the continued viability of the sovereign state.

This discussion therefore, centers on whether the concept of sovereignty is still viable in the face of these challenges.

2. NATURE AND HISTORY OF SOVEREIGNTY

Nicholas has outlined four main features of sovereignty: First, a sovereign state is one that enjoys supreme political authority and enjoys exclusive right over the legitimate use of force within its territory. Secondly, it is capable of exercising control of movements across its borders. Thirdly, it can make its foreign policy choices freely and finally, it is recognized by other governments as an independent entity entitled to freedom from external intervention.⁴ Today, these features of sovereignty are being challenged in a numbers of ways. This may not be immediately obvious because Sovereignty is so fundamentally embedded in the way the world works that its existence is often taken for granted.

As a hallmark of statehood, territorial sovereignty⁵ underlies the system of international order in relations among states. An act of aggression is unlawful, not only because it undermines international order, but because states have exercised their sovereignty to outlaw war. In addition, the failure or weakness of state capacity that brings about a political vacuum within states leads to human tragedies and

³a. Brerstaker. T. J and Weber. Eds *State Sovereignty as Social Construct*: (New York; Cambridge University Press, 1996) pg. 6

b. In 1949 the International Court of Justice (ICT) observed that “between Independent States, respect for territorial Sovereignty is an essential foundation of international relations.” See ICJ Reports, 1949. Pg. 4

⁴ Onuf, N.G, “Sovereignty: Outline of a Conceptual History.” *Alternatives: Global, Local, Political*, vol. 16, no. 4, 1991, pp.425–46. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40644726>. Accessed 20 Aug. 2024.

⁵ Stiliz, A., “Territorial sovereignty: A brief introduction” *Journal of Social Philosophy*, Volume 52, Issue 1, (2021) 1-52. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josp.12404>.

international and regional insecurity. Repressive, aggressive, or failed states may result in threats to international peace and security. The principle of non-interference in affairs that are within the domestic jurisdiction of states is the anchor to state sovereignty within the system of international relations and obligations.⁶

Jurisdiction broadly refers to the power, authority, and competence of a state to govern persons and property within its territory. Jurisdiction is either "prescriptive" or "enforcement".⁷ Prescriptive jurisdiction relates to the power of a state to make or prescribe law within and outside its territory, while enforcement jurisdiction is about the power of the state to implement the law within its territory. Jurisdiction exercised by states is then the corollary of their sovereignty. Jurisdiction is clearly founded on territorial sovereignty but extends beyond it. Jurisdiction is *prima facie* exclusive over a state's territory and population, and the general duty of non-intervention in domestic affairs protects both the territorial sovereignty and the domestic jurisdiction of states on an equal basis. This paper examines what history was before the territorial state became the main bearer of rights and responsibilities within the international society during the 17th and 18th centuries.

The international system was not always arranged in terms of States having international legal personality and exclusive political authority. Throughout the middle ages, political authority was shared by empires, kingdoms, duchies, and city-states. Complicating matters further, there was no clear boundary separating religious from secular authorities. Popes and kings claimed and fought over the same peoples and territories. This patchwork of overlapping authorities became unreliable when wars of religion followed the brake up of Catholicism⁸. According to Bartelson Jens, this was the world that inspired Thomas Hobbes when he imagined life in a state of nature. For most people, life was nasty, poor, brutish, and short.⁹ In response, European rulers came to embrace sovereignty as a means to maintain a basic level of order within and among individual countries and in relations between and amongst

⁶ Naigen, Z., "The Principle of Non-interference and its Application in Practices of Contemporary International Law" *Fudan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, Volume 9, (2016) 449-464. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40647-016-0126-y>

⁷ Ryngaert, C. "Introduction", *Jurisdiction in International Law*, *Oxford Monographs in International Law* (Oxford, 2008; online (edn) Oxford Academic, 1 Jan. 2009), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199544714.003.0001>, (Retrieved 20 Aug, 2024).

⁸ Bartelson Jens, *A Genealogy of Sovereignty* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1995) p. 13

⁹ *Ibid*

them. A landmark event in this era was the Peace of Westphalia of 1648, which recognized that states had certain inherent rights, namely, exclusive jurisdiction within their own territory, political independence, and full equality under international law, including the right to conduct foreign policy. Sovereignty ushered the norm against interference in the domestic affairs of other states.¹⁰

The post-1945 system of international order enshrined in the Charter of the United Nations Organization inherited this basic model and also ushered in an era of change. For example, in accordance with Article 2 (1) of the Charter of the United Nations, the world organization is based on the principle of sovereign equality of all member states. While they are equal in relation to one another and completely sovereign in accordance with Article 2 (7), their status of legal equality as a mark of sovereignty is also the basis on which the United Nations Organization is established and endowed with capacity to act between and within states.

Paradoxically, the current transformation and gradual circumscription of the sovereign state which began roughly after the Second World War and continued to the present, also owes its development to the United Nations system. Admittedly much of international law, at least until the Second World¹¹ War was designed to reinforce sovereignty.

However, driven by the horrors of the Nazi genocide and the lessons of the Nuremberg war crimes tribunal, the society of states forged a series of agreements under the auspices of the United Nations that committed states to protect the human rights of their own citizens - a restriction on authority of sovereign states.¹² The post-war period also saw the growth of intergovernmental organizations helping in governing interstate relations in areas ranging from trade and monetary policy to security,

¹⁰ Leo, G. "The American Journal of International Law" Vol. 42, No. 1 (Jan., 1948), pp. 20-41

¹¹ Between 1945-46, several German war criminals were indicted and hanged by The Nuremberg Tribunal, established by the Allied Forces, on the charges amongst others, of genocide, meaning the extermination of racial or religious groups especially the Jews, Poles, Gypsies, and others. The Germans had embarked upon a gigantic plan to permanently change the population balance in occupied Europe in their favor. They intended to wipe out entirely the biological capacity of the neighbors of Germany so that Germany might win a permanent victory. In that attempt, 6 million Jews were exterminated.

¹² See for example, Statute of the International Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia 1993, Statute of the International Tribunal for Rwanda 1994, Statute of the International Criminal Court 2002, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1976, International Convention Concerning the Treatment of Prisoners of War 1932, Genocide Convention of 1948, Geneva Convention of August 12, 1949 Relative to the Protection of Civilians, Geneva Convention August 12, 1949 Relative to the treatment of prisoners of War, Geneva Convention of August 12, 1949 for the Amelioration of the condition of Wounded, Sick and Shipwrecked members of Armed Forces at Sea,

environment, telecommunication, science and technology, drugs, and narcotics. At the same time, much of the non-Western world gained their independence in the decades after World War II, setting up a scenario in which many of the new states were not fully sovereign.¹³ Granting former colonies independence and recognizing them as sovereign states, they joined intergovernmental organizations and were ostensibly the equals of European states. At the same time, there was a general lack of capacity to govern the state, combined with arbitrarily drawn borders that left many emerging groups frustrated while trying to provide a government with supreme authority. Today, sovereignty is essentially based on borders, not on any capacity on the part of governments. This was adopted because it was the only means for so many colonies to become independent quickly.¹⁴

3. RESTRICTIONS ON SOVEREIGNTY:

i. United Nations Charter

The Charter highlights tension between the sovereignty, independence, and equality of individual states, on the one hand, and collective international obligations for the maintenance of international peace and security, on the other hand.¹⁵ According to Chapter VII, sovereignty is not a barrier to action taken by the Security Council as part of measures in response to "a threat to the peace, a breach of the peace, or an act of aggression." In other words, the sovereignty of states, as recognized in the United Nations Charter, yields to the demands of international peace and security and the principle of sovereign equality only holds effectively for each state when there is stability, peace, and order among states. Consequently, state sovereignty may be limited by customary and treaty obligations in international relations and law. States are legally responsible for the performance of their international obligations, and state sovereignty therefore cannot be an excuse for their non-performance. Obligations assumed by states by virtue of their membership in the United Nations and the

¹³ Thomas, M. and Thompson, A. "Empire and Globalisation: from 'High Imperialism' to Decolonisation", *The International History Review*, Volume 36, Issue 1 (2013), pp. 142–170. doi: 10.1080/07075332.2013.828643.

¹⁴ Jackson, R. H. (New York: Cambridge University, 1990). *Quasi-States: Sovereignty, International Relations, and the Third World*.

¹⁵ Quoted by Shashi Tharoor and Sam Daws, "Humanitarian Intervention: Getting Past the Reefs," *World Policy Journal* XVIII, no. 2 (2001), p.25.

corresponding powers of the world organization presuppose a restriction of the sovereignty of member states to the extent of their obligations under the Charter.

Specifically, Article 1 (2) stipulates that "all Members, in order to ensure to all of them the rights and benefits resulting from membership, shall fulfill in good faith the obligations assumed by them in accordance with the present Charter." Furthermore, under "Purposes and Principles," this same article provides that member states are obliged to achieve international cooperation in solving problems of an economic, social, cultural, or humanitarian character and in promoting and encouraging respect for human rights and for fundamental freedoms for all, without distinction as to race, sex, language, or religion. This article further recognizes the United Nations as a centre for harmonizing the actions of states in the attainment of these common ends. Thus, the Charter elevates the solution of economic, social, cultural, and humanitarian problems, as well as human rights, to the international sphere. By definition, these matters cannot be said to be exclusively domestic, and solutions cannot be located exclusively within the sovereignty of states.

Sovereignty therefore carries with it primary responsibilities for states to protect persons and property and to discharge the functions of government adequately within their territories. The quality and range of responsibilities for governance have brought about significant changes in state sovereignty since 1945. In particular, since the signing of the United Nations Charter, there has been an expanding network of obligations in the field of human rights. These create a dense set of state obligations to protect persons and property, as well as to regulate political and economic affairs. Sovereignty is incapable, then, of completely shielding internal violations of human rights that contradict international obligations.

Similarly, Article 2 (7) of the Charter is also subject to widely accepted limits. Analytically, the words "*essentially* within the domestic jurisdiction of States" refer to those matters that are not regulated by international law. As the ICJ has concluded, "The question whether a certain matter is or is not solely within the domestic jurisdiction of a State is an essentially relative question; it depends on the development of international relations."¹⁶ The ICJ has further concluded that it hardly seems

¹⁶ Christopher M. Ryan, "Sovereignty, Intervention, and the Law: A Tenuous Relationship of Competing Principles," *Millennium: Journal of International Studies* Vol.26 (1997), p.77; and Samuel M. Makinda,

conceivable that terms like "domestic jurisdiction" were intended to have a fixed content, regardless of the subsequent evolution of international law.¹⁷

Sovereignty has been eroded by contemporary economic, cultural, and environmental factors. Interference in what would previously have been regarded as internal affairs — by other states, the private sector, and non-state actors has become routine. However, the preoccupation here is not these routine matters but the potential tension when the norm of state sovereignty and egregious human suffering coexist.

ii. Self determination

The principle of self-determination is enshrined in the United Nations Charter¹⁸ and other international instruments created under the umbrella of the United Nations, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights.¹⁹ It has been recognized in other international and regional human rights instruments including the Helsinki Final Act, 1975,²⁰ and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Right, 1981²¹.

According to Gasiokwu,

“The right of self-determination occupies an exceptional position in the catalogue of human and peoples’ rights. Without any exaggeration, it can be labeled “the right of rights” because it is the prerequisite for the enjoyment of any human and peoples’ rights. The denial of the right to self-determination rules out automatically the possibility of enjoyment of the remaining human and peoples’ rights.”²²

It is worthy of note that in spite of its exceptional importance and its recognition in various international and regional instruments, the principle of self-determination is

“Sovereignty and International Security: Challenges for the United Nations,” *Global Governance vol.2*, no. 2 (May – August 1996), p.149.

¹⁷ Aegean Sea Case, in ICJ Reports, 1978, pg. 32

¹⁸ Articles (2), 55, 73 and 76

¹⁹ The Right of Self-Determination is embodied in Article 1 (1) of both Covenants which contain identical provision on self-determination; the Covenants were adopted in 1966 and came into force in 1976.

²⁰ Paragraph viii

²¹ Article 20(1) and (2)

²² M.O.U Gasiokwu. Human Rights: history, Ideology and Law.(Jos: FAB Educational Books, 2003)pg.230

conceptually bedeviled by a lot of problems which cumulatively question the relationship between self-determination, and the sanctity and preservation of the Sovereign state. For example, which of these two concepts (self-determination or State Sovereignty) does international law protect or is supposed to protect? What is the practical scope of this right and at what stage is the right exercisable? Whatever the answers to these questions may be, the quest for self-determination reduces the state's legitimacy and capacity to translate their nominal sovereignty into effective governance. Some weak states find themselves confronting insurgents bent on their overthrow or warlords seeking to dominate ungoverned regions.

Neighboring states may exploit these vulnerabilities to foment rebellion or secessionist movements. Even where unified states exist, government institutions may be crippled by corruption or captured by criminals. When states cannot exercise their sovereign powers, they court instability, even anarchy. They may collapse entirely and enter the category of "failed states."

Until recently, the international community viewed states with a sovereignty deficit primarily through a humanitarian lens refusing to appreciate the connection between failed state and their national security. For example, during the 1990s, the conflict in Somalia and Afghanistan presented no apparent strategic relevance to international peace but after the attacks of September 11, 2001 the world was reminded that weak states can threaten international security as much as strong ones, by providing breeding grounds for extremism and havens for criminals, drug traffickers, and terrorists. Such lawlessness abroad can bring devastation into a state, so, preventing today's troubled countries from becoming tomorrow's failed states, is an international imperative.

How should the world respond when weak states lack sovereign capacities? In extraordinary circumstances, when a country collapses or is unprepared for formal independence, the world community may need to assume many of the responsibilities of a sovereign government. This was the role the United Nations played in East Timor—helping it make the transition from a disputed province of Indonesia to a fully independent state. Halfway around the world, the United Nations and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) served as the custodians of sovereignty in

Kosovo, before the determination of its final status, just as the African Union served during the conflict in Liberia.

iii. **Globalization**

The third great challenge to sovereignty is posed by globalization. Globalization is the sum total of connections and interactions in political, economic, social, and cultural spheres which compress distance and increase the permeability of traditional boundaries to the rapid flow of goods, capital, people, ideas, and information. It goes beyond simple interdependence, which implies that states affect one another. It describes an explosion of cross-border transactions and flows, driven primarily by non-state actors that frequently operate outside the effective control of national governments. Globalization helps in enhancing the capacity of all states to police their frontiers, regulate cross-border flows, and protect citizens from foreign threats. Besides providing tangible goods, globalization also facilitates the importation of bad manners. The same networks that channel billions of dollars in investment capital around the world every day can also transmit financial diseases.²³ The same structure of global production that brings opportunity to poor regions can generate trans-boundary pollution. The same Internet that links continents can be used to coordinate criminal enterprises. The same flow of scientific expertise that enables medical breakthroughs can put the power to kill thousands in the hands of terrorists.

Globalization requires regulation. Governments must devote political will and resources to regain sovereign control over cross-border flows that endanger their well-being and security. National governments must act alone at times, but mostly with others to track down terrorist networks, attack the global drug trade, end trafficking in human beings, stem the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, control the spread of infectious diseases, and mitigate the destabilizing impact of rapid financial flows. The global struggle against terrorism shows how the international community is adapting the conceptions of sovereignty to deal with today's threats.²⁴ National

²³ The present global economic recession is believed to have been triggered by the failure of American mortgage Institution.

²⁴ United Nations Convention on Terrorism. See also OAU Convention on the prevention and containing of Terrorism, adopted in Algeria 1999 and entered into force in December 2003. The Convention distinguished between terrorism and armed struggle for self-determination. See also protocol to the OAU convention on the prevention and combating of Terrorism, 2004.

governments have also supported initiatives to combat money laundering by criminals and corrupt politicians by helping to repatriate stolen monies.²⁵

Finally, the international community is responding to infectious diseases that threaten the lives of millions and in this regard the United States and Europe have offered the largest single contribution to the Global Fund to Fight HIV/AIDS, Tuberculosis, and Malaria in Africa - an innovative public-private partnership established to battle the world's most dangerous plagues.

iv. **Delegating Sovereignty:**

The fourth challenge to sovereignty is the trend toward voluntarily pooling or delegating sovereign rights to gain the benefits of multilateral cooperation. As the distinction between "foreign" and "domestic" fades and as national economies become more integrated with global markets, all peoples and governments are finding it harder to achieve security, prosperity, and wellbeing through purely national efforts.²⁶ The mentality of ceding sovereignty voluntarily can be very challenging, as citizens imagine the implications for their national identity and democratic institutions. This is apparent today in Europe, where countries are relinquishing independence to a degree not seen before. In a step inconceivable two generations ago, the mark, franc, and lira as distinct currencies have been replaced by the euro. Even as it plans a new round of expansion, the European Union is presently drafting a federal constitution that is likely to require extensive grants of sovereignty from national governments to a stronger European Parliament, Commission, and Council and perhaps even a European president.

²⁵ e.g. The European Commission Directive on Money Laundering 91/308/EEC, implemented by England through the Criminal Justice Act 1993 and Money Laundering Regulation 1993, cited by G. Moffat's *Trust Law* 2nd ed. (London; Butterworth 1994)p.577, The Vienna Convention of 1982 introducing an international platform for repatriation of looted funds, the African Union (AU) Convention on Prevention and Combating corruption, 2003: The philosophy that underlies the Partnership for Africans' Development (NEPAD) Declaration, 2001 and Memorandum of Understanding on the African Peer Review Mechanism, 2003, are structured to introduce transparency in governance with a view to eliminating corruption. See O.F. Emiri & A.O. Giwa's *Global Money Trail: a Comparative Reflection in Emiri F. and Deinduoma (ed.) Law, Oil, and Contemporary Development Issues in Nigeria: Essays in honor of Late Justice Emmanuel, Joel Igonoware*, (Lagos: Malthouse Press Limited, 2008) Pp.331-359

²⁶ It was expected that as the world moves towards global economic integration, all the market economies of the world would mutually benefit from the new global economic arrangement. Samuel Ojogbo however discussed how such globalization impacts negatively in developing economy in his paper "The Fallacy of Global Corporate Governance Convergence" in Emiri, O.F and Deinduoma O.G. op.cit, Pp 305-330. According to the writer, the dominance of major market economies, and the continual circulation of capital within them, suggests exclusion of developing market economies from the emerging global economic setting.

This transformation is reminiscent of (and potentially as profound as) the transition that Nigeria made more than thirty years ago, when we moved from a loose collection of regions under the pre-independent constitutions to a federation union under the Federal Constitution of 1979.

International order depends on Cooperation among sovereign states and this is possible only if they accept some restraints on their conduct and recognize reciprocal obligations. This raises the question: When should a country delegate some of its sovereignty to join in multilateral institutions or treaties? The most reasonable answer is: whether the benefits of a proposed arrangement, which may include greater predictability, burden-sharing, and international legitimacy outweigh the costs including lost policy autonomy and flexibility.

Take the case of trade. During the 1930s, countries tried to reduce unemployment and increase domestic output by raising prohibitive tariffs and other barriers to imports, as well as by competitive devaluation of their currencies in order to encourage exports and discourage imports. Other countries soon retaliated in kind. Global commerce collapsed, and the world spiraled downward into the Great Depression. Recognizing the peril of policies in which everyone loses, the United States in the late 1940s spearheaded the creation of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade, or GATT, a forum for mutually agreed reductions in trade barriers. GATT proved wildly successful.²⁷

The creation of the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 1995 introduced a robust multilateral system to resolving trade disputes. Under this arrangement, WTO members must submit complaints to a binding dispute settlement mechanism, instead of taking action unilaterally. If members fail to comply, they must either provide mutually acceptable compensation or open themselves to sanctions accordingly. States support this system of resolving disputes not necessarily because they feel certain that the tribunal will always rule in their favor, but because their consumers, exporters, and investors have a fundamental interest in an open trading system governed by the rule of law. In a similar vein, the industrialized nations voluntarily gave up some freedom of action in ratifying the Chemical Weapons Convention. The CWC is the first

²⁷Khor, M. *Rethinking Globalization: Critical Issues and Policy Choices*. (New York: Zed Books.; 1999) Korten, D. 1996. *When Corporations Rule the World*. (Bloom field CT: Kumarian Press, 1996).

international agreement to outlaw the production, transfer, and use of an entire class of weapons (poison gas). Its inspection regime is intrusive, requiring all parties to open their military installations and chemical industry facilities to international scrutiny.

v. Humanitarian Concern:

The final challenge to sovereignty arises not when states cede it voluntarily, but when it is taken away. This is the result of one of the most significant developments of the past decades. The emerging global consensus is that sovereignty is not a blank check. Rather, sovereign status is contingent on the fulfillment by each state of certain fundamental obligations, both to its own citizens and to the international community. When a regime fails to live up to these responsibilities or abuses its prerogatives, it risks forfeiting its sovereign privileges, including, in extreme cases, its immunity from armed intervention. The exceptions to the norm of non-intervention are warranted in at least three circumstances.

The first qualification of sovereignty comes when a state commits or fails to prevent genocide or crimes against humanity on its territory. The international community then has the right and, indeed, in some cases, the obligation to act to safeguard the lives of innocents. According to Gasiokwu:

The problems of human rights have always caused great difficulties in the drawing of a borderline between the responsibilities of the society and the state at the municipal level and between the responsibilities of the sovereign state and international community at international level. Historically, since the emergence of modern states, there have been accorded a high degree of exclusive competence over people, resources, and events within their boundaries, expressed in the principles of sovereignty. How a particular state, treats its own nationals was long regarded as an internal affair of the particular state beyond the reach of international law and of other states. In recent times, however, that traditional set up was shattered by the emergence of the contemporary international law of human rights. As a result, international community claims the right to inquire into how a particular state treats, not merely aliens, but all individuals within

*its boundaries, including its own nationals, considering it a matter of "International concern".*²⁸

Governments that commit such offenses or out of choice or weakness allow such offenses to occur must be held to account. Non-intervention is no longer sacrosanct, even at the United Nations, a body formed by and committed to sovereign states. As U.N. Secretary-General Kofi Annan declared in September 1999, "States bent on criminal behavior should know that frontiers are not an absolute defense, that massive and systematic violations of human rights wherever they may take place should not be allowed to stand."

Within the African continent, there is a recognition that sovereignty must have limits. This is evident in the founding Act of the African Union, which replaced the Organization of African Unity (OAU). In contrast to the OAU, which regarded non-interference as a bedrock principle, the new African Union commits all members to respect human rights and good governance, establishing a peer review mechanism to monitor compliance with these commitments.²⁹ Within the Western Hemisphere, the members of the Organization of American States except Cuba have committed to a Democratic Charter, pledging to oppose any interruption of democratic processes.

There is also a comparable change in international views of state responsibilities to fight terrorism. This is the second point of growing global consensus. Quite simply, countries have the right to take action to protect their citizens against those states that abet, support, or harbor international terrorists, or are incapable of controlling terrorists operating from their territory. States risk forfeiting their sovereignty when they take steps that represent a clear threat to global security, when certain regimes with a history of aggression and support for terrorism pursue weapons of mass destruction, thereby endangering the international community, they jeopardize their

²⁸Gasiokwu, Op. Cit., Pp.219-220

²⁹ See the AU Convention on Prevention and Combating Corruption, 2003. Noteworthy of mention, corruption as described in Art. 4 covers a range of practices which includes bribes in all forms, by public and private officials and persons. Combative remedies including confiscation and seizure of illicit proceeds and instrumentalities of corruption-see Art. 16. Interestingly, the philosophy that underlies the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) Declaration, 2001 and Memorandum of Understanding on the African Peer Review Mechanism, 2003, are structured to introduce transparency in governance and business with a view of eliminating corruption.

sovereign immunity from intervention including anticipatory action to destroy this developing capability.

The right to self-defense including the right to take "pre-emptive" action against a clear and imminent threat has long been recognized in international law and practice. The challenge today is to adapt the principle of self-defense to the unique dangers posed by the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction. Traditionally, international lawyers have distinguished between pre-emption against an imminent threat, which they consider legitimate, and "preventive action" taken against a developing capability, which they regard as problematic. This conventional distinction has begun to break down, however. The deception practiced by rogue regimes has made it harder to discern either the capability or imminence of attack. It is also often difficult to interpret the intentions of certain states, encouraging judgement against a backdrop of past aggressive behavior.

4. THE RESPONSIBILITIES OF SOVEREIGNTY:

In all three of the situations that have been outlined- stopping human rights abuses and genocide, fighting terrorism, and preventing the spread of weapons of mass destruction, the principle remains the same. With rights come obligations. Sovereignty is not absolute. It is conditional. When states violate minimum standards by committing, permitting, or threatening intolerable acts against their own people or other nations, then some of the privileges of sovereignty are forfeited.

The world is still moving towards consensus on the obligations of sovereignty and on the steps that are warranted when states refuse to live up to them. In all cases, the bar to armed intervention must be set high. It cannot be a blanket response to every unsavory despot. The reason for prudence is clear-cut. Although sovereignty is less absolute and more contingent than in the past, it remains, as it has been for the past three-and-a-half centuries, a central pillar – and arguably the central pillar of world order. The world does not want to return to a situation in which governments routinely intervene in one another's affairs. In an age of advanced conventional weapons and new instruments of mass destruction, this would be a recipe for catastrophe. Accordingly, there should be a general presumption in favor of respecting sovereignty. The answer to this paradox is to strike a new balance between the rights and responsibilities of states. This new conception of sovereignty must adjust to the needs

of weak states, adapt to the forces of globalization, accommodate the need for cooperation, and address the problem of outlawed regimes.

5. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper is to analyze debates on the changing nature of state sovereignty. State sovereignty has for the past several hundred years been a defining principle of inter-state relations and a foundation of World order. The concept lies at the heart of both customary international law and United Nations (UN) Charter. It remains both an essential component of the maintenance of international peace and co-operation, and a defense of weak state against the strong.³⁰ However, it is also one of the most poorly understood concepts in international relations. The confusion emerges from two sources. First, as was revealed, sovereignty is in fact a relatively recent innovation connected to the emergence of the nation states as the primary unit of political organization. Second, a number of contemporary issues have placed increasing limit on the exercise of sovereign authority. For example, in today's globalized world, it is generally recognized that cultural, environmental, and economic influences neither respect borders nor require an entry visa. At the same time, not only have technology and communication made borders permeable, but the political dimensions of internal disorder and suffering have also often resulted in greater international disorder.²⁶

The combinations of these factors have challenged the fixity of the concept of State sovereignty often assumed by scholars of International Relations. A more sophisticated view of sovereignty now envisions State and non-State actors in a continual process of negotiating the nature of sovereignty.³¹ The rise of private transnational and supranational institutions such as the World Trade Organization, The European and The African Unions, and the Universal Human Rights Covenants, place a partial de-nationalization of national territories. These quasi-legal institutions now have the power and legitimacy to demand accountability from national authorities with the ironic twist that both depend upon the state to enforce their goals.

³⁰Nico Shrijver, "The Changing Nature of State Sovereignty" *The British Year Book of International Law* (Oxford; Clarendon Press, 2000), PP. 69 – 70

³¹ "sovereignty," *Beyond Intractability*. Eds. Guy Burgess and Heidi Burgess. (Conflict Research Consortium; University of Colorado, Boulder. Posted: September 2004) at <http://www.beyonintractability.org/essay/sovereignty/>. Posted